

METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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Annotation. Critical thinking skills are essential to succeed in today's world. The ability to think critically enables individuals to analyze information effectively, make informed decisions, and solve complex problems. As such, high school students must develop these skills as they prepare for college and the workforce. English classes offer an excellent opportunity for students to develop critical thinking skills, and educators can use various methodologies to achieve this goal.

Key words: critical thinking, internet, technology, education, foreign languages, games, AI, reading, literature, debate.

МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ НАВЫКОВ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ СТАРШЕКЛАССНИКОВ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. Навыки критического мышления необходимы для достижения успеха в современном мире. Способность мыслить критически позволяет людям эффективно анализировать информацию, принимать обоснованные решения и решать сложные проблемы. Таким образом, старшеклассники должны развивать эти навыки, готовясь к колледжу и работе. Уроки английского языка дают учащимся прекрасную возможность развить навыки критического мышления, а преподаватели могут использовать различные методики для достижения этой цели.

Ключевые слова: критическое мышление, интернет, технологии, образование, иностранные языки, игры, ИИ, чтение, литература, дебаты.

INTRODUCTION

The development of critical thinking skills is crucial for high school students, as it allows them to analyze information, make informed decisions, and solve problems effectively. English classes are an ideal setting for the development of these skills, as they provide students with opportunities to engage with literature and other texts in a critical manner. This article will explore the methodology of developing critical thinking skills of high school students in English classes.

The first step in developing critical thinking skills is to create a learning environment that encourages questioning and inquiry. Teachers should encourage students to ask questions and challenge assumptions about the texts they are studying. This can be done through class discussions, debates, and other interactive activities that encourage students to think critically about the material.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Another important aspect of developing critical thinking skills is to teach students how to analyze and evaluate information. This involves teaching them how to identify biases, assumptions, and fallacies in arguments, as well as how to evaluate evidence and draw conclusions based on that evidence. Teachers can use a variety of techniques, such as case studies, role-playing exercises, and group projects, to help students develop these skills.

In addition to teaching analytical skills, teachers should also encourage students to be creative and innovative in their thinking. This can be done through activities such as brainstorming

sessions, where students are encouraged to come up with new and creative ideas. Teachers can also use writing assignments, such as essays or research papers, to help students develop their critical thinking skills by requiring them to analyze and evaluate information in a structured and organized manner.

The following are some of the methodologies that educators can use to develop critical thinking skills in high school students in English classes:

1. Socratic Dialogue Method

Socratic Dialogue is a method used to stimulate critical thinking skills in students. It involves questioning students to help them analyze the information they have learned. Educators can use this method in English classes by asking students to critically analyze literary works. Teachers can use this method to encourage students to think beyond what they have read and to encourage them to consider the author's motives and the message conveyed in the literature.

2. Contextual Reading Method

The Contextual Reading method involves analyzing texts within their contexts. In English classes, this method can be applied by providing students with real-world scenarios that require them to think critically. By challenging students to apply the lessons they have learned in English classes to real-world situations, educators can help students develop critical thinking skills that they can use throughout their lives.

3. Literature Circles Method

The Literature Circles method is an excellent way to encourage students to think critically about literature. In this method, students are divided into small groups, and each group is assigned a specific reading task. Each group member is then required to read the text and share their thoughts and insights with the group. This approach encourages students to think critically about the literature they are reading and to analyze the author's message.

4. Debate Method

The Debate method is an excellent way to encourage critical thinking skills in students. It involves presenting students with a controversial topic and encouraging them to argue both sides of the debate. In English classes, this method can be used to encourage students to analyze literature from multiple perspectives.

5. Collaborative Learning Method

Collaborative Learning is a method that involves students working together to solve problems. In English classes, this method can be used to encourage students to think critically about literature. By working together to analyze a text, students can learn from each other's insights and develop a deeper understanding of the literature.

6. Problem-Based Learning Method

Problem-Based Learning is a method that involves students solving real-world problems. In English classes, this method can be used to encourage students to apply their critical thinking skills to real-world scenarios. By analyzing literature from a problem-solving perspective, students can develop critical thinking skills that they can use in any situation.

7. Inquiry-Based Learning Method

Inquiry-Based Learning is a method that involves students asking questions to solve problems. In English classes, this method can be used to encourage students to ask questions about literature and to think critically about the answers. By analyzing literature through an inquiry-based approach, students can develop critical thinking skills that they can use in any situation.

RESULTS

Finally, teachers should provide students with feedback on their critical thinking skills. This can be done through assessments that measure their ability to analyze information, evaluate evidence, and draw conclusions based on that evidence. Teachers can also provide feedback on written assignments, such as essays or research papers, by highlighting areas where students need to improve their critical thinking skills.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the development of critical thinking skills is crucial for high school students, and English classes provide an ideal setting for this development. By creating a learning environment that encourages questioning and inquiry, teaching analytical skills, encouraging creativity and innovation, and providing feedback on student performance, teachers can help students develop the critical thinking skills they need to succeed in school and beyond. The methodologies outlined above provide educators with various approaches to developing critical thinking skills in high school students in English classes. By using these methodologies, educators can help students develop the critical thinking skills they need to succeed in college and the workforce.

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